

The Impact of a Social-Emotional Learning Curriculum on English Language Arts Achievement

Michael G. Hylan, Ph.D.
Associate Professor in Graduate Studies
Anderson University
Anderson, SC

Abstract

This study explored the impact of a social-emotional learning (SEL) literacy curriculum on the English Language Arts (ELA) achievement of elementary-age students attending public, high-poverty schools. Schools classified as high-poverty schools have more than 75 percent of the students eligible for free or reduced-price lunch. The subjects for the study consisted of students attending 10 elementary schools in the Miami Dade Public School System, all having been designated as "persistently lowest-achieving" by the Education Transformation Office of the Florida Department of Education. Nine of the 10 schools had free or reduced-price lunch populations over 90%, with some schools as high as 99%, and all were classified Title 1. The results revealed that there was a statistically significant difference between the numbers of students scoring proficient or above on the state ELA standardized exam in the schools using a SEL-based literacy curriculum program versus those using a traditional curriculum.

Keywords: social-emotional, literacy, English Language Arts, at-risk

Introduction

Today's public schools are exceedingly focused on the academic achievement of students, as seen by an ongoing emphasis on standardized testing and initiatives such as No Child Left Behind and Race to the Top. However, schools have an equally important role in guiding healthy, well-rounded students, which not only includes students' academic abilities but their social and emotional development as well (Jacobson, 2018). Students who lack the knowledge and ability to deal with social, emotional, and mental health issues often turn to risk-taking behaviors leading to a lack of academic success in school (Weissberg et al., 2015). For that reason, many experts have recommended that schools implement a social-emotional learning program within the curriculum with an equal emphasis placed on it as academic success (Armstrong, 2016). According to the Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL)(2024), successful implementation of social-emotional learning (SEL) strategies in schools has been documented as playing a role in improving academic achievement and school connectedness.

Literature Review

One of the greatest impacts of SEL is its positive influence on students' attitudes. Children who have strong SEL skills are able to maintain more positive relationships with peers and adults due to increased awareness of pro-social behavior, which leads to a reduction in aggressive behaviors towards others (CASEL, 2024), resulting in more time spent in school and the classroom. In addition, the mental health of students is strengthened as they are able to make emotionally strong decisions through effective problem-solving. Effective problem-solving skills correlate with student ability to achieve academically.

When SEL is addressed at a school level, positive student behavior and relationships increase and positively influence school connectedness (Wilkins et al., 2023). The consistent patterns in the interactions, relationships, behavior, and thinking of the teachers, administrators, staff, and students (Wilkins et al., 2023; Schonert-Reichl, 2017; Jones & Bouffard, 2012) can define school climate and culture. There are several benefits to a positive school climate and overall connectedness. Relationships between students and staff are stronger, leaving students feeling safe and comfortable in their learning environment. There are fewer behavioral issues, such as bullying and delinquency. Lastly, there is a reduction in emotional stress that leads to depression and social withdrawal (Center for Social and Emotional Education, 2010).

Because social and emotional deficiencies can hinder a student's chance of success in the classroom, the potential impact of social-emotional learning on academic achievement is heightened. Academic and SEL skills are thought to develop and operate together because SEL skills increase students' capability to learn. Students with strong SEL skills set high academic goals for themselves and have the self-discipline, self-confidence, motivation, and organization to obtain them. They can utilize problem-solving skills, higher-order thinking skills, and critical thinking skills to address obstacles and become better decision-makers when it comes to schoolwork. These same skills follow students into adulthood and careers. Effectual SEL skills provide these future adults with the work habits, values, and abilities necessary for postsecondary education, careers, and becoming responsible citizens (Dymnicki et al., 2013; Yoder, 2014).

Experts in SEL agree that simply implementing strategies and lessons on

social-emotional learning is insufficient for success. SEL needs to be well-executed, with several key factors in place. They include explicit teaching of the skills, integration of skills within the curriculum, and time for application of skills (Wilkins et al., 2023; Schonert-Reichl, 2017; Weissberg et al., 2015).

Just as students need to be taught math and reading strategies, students need explicit instruction regarding SEL. For this systematic learning process to occur, there needs to be established policies and guidelines, involved school leaders, and ongoing professional development for teachers and administrators (Weissberg et al., 2015). With a natural partnership between SEL and academic success, SEL skills should be naturally incorporated into the curriculum (Schonert-Reichl, 2017; Weissberg et al., 2015).

In addition to teaching SEL skills, students need to be given the opportunity to apply and practice them. This includes daily interactions within the classroom as well as in the halls, lunchroom, playground, and special areas. The goal is for students to use SEL skills “as part of their daily repertoire of behaviors” (Durlak et al., 2011, p. 408). School staff and faculty should recognize students who use SEL skills as a way to reinforce and promote learning. Incorporation of skills is most efficiently done in safe and nurturing learning environments (CASEL, 2024; Weissberg & Cascarion, 2013)

According to the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES) (2020), high-poverty schools are defined as “public schools where more than 75 percent of the students are eligible for free or reduced-price lunch (FRPL)” (p. 1 endnote). While research reflects the positive benefits of SEL on all children, there is a specific need in high-poverty schools. Data reflects that the many challenges teachers face in high-

poverty schools are at higher rates than for their counterparts in medium and low-poverty schools. For example, according to the NCES (2020), students from high-poverty schools scored lower than students from low-poverty schools in both reading and math on fourth and eighth-grade assessments. In addition, dropout rates are much higher at high-poverty schools and districts.

Research reveals that, due to their behavioral and emotional growth, students attending high-poverty schools implementing comprehensive SEL programs showed more improved social skills and higher grade point averages than students in similar schools not participating in SEL (Murray & Malmgren, 2005). A study conducted on teachers’ attitudes and perceptions of SEL by Bridgeland et al. (2013) demonstrated that teachers in high-poverty schools reported more positive student-teacher relationships and stronger student academic performance. These skills will follow them into adulthood, with the possibility of a continued and lasting impact on poverty levels.

Method

Research Question

This study sought to explore the impact of implementing an SEL literacy-based curriculum on the academic achievement in English Language Arts (ELA) of elementary-age students attending public, high-poverty schools. Because the focus of this research study was on SEL learning in high-poverty schools, the ten elementary schools chosen for the study had a greater than 75% free and reduced lunch rate, with some schools as high as 99%, and all were classified Title 1. The SEL literacy curriculum chosen for this study was the *Cloud9World’s Elementary Core* program.

Accordingly, the research question investigated in this study was “what is the impact of a SEL literacy-based curriculum on academic achievement in ELA in high poverty public elementary school settings?” Of note, the schools chosen for inclusion in this study were classified as persistently low achieving schools by the Education Transformation Office (ETO) of the Florida Department of Education. All ten schools are part of the Miami-Dade Public Schools system.

Research Design

For this study, a quasi-experimental matched-pair research design using archival data was utilized. This approach, using a non-equivalent groups design, established a control group and treatment group based on school decision to implement or not implement the *Cloud9World* curriculum. While random assignment is the optimal procedure for establishing equivalence of groups on both measured and unmeasured characteristics that may be associated with outcomes, it was not practical for this study due to the use of archival data. Thus, any post-intervention differences between groups in outcomes were evaluated using statistical analysis measures that adjust for baseline equivalence factors.

The primary threat to demonstrating the causal effects of treatment in the study could easily have been selection bias by the researchers conducting the study. If left to researcher discretion, it is quite possible that those schools whose students already had a low rate of academic success or other impacting factors would have been selected as treatment schools. Treatment schools were selected simply because they elected to implement the *Cloud9World* program school-wide. This was important because it would be quite possible that administrators would specifically assign the SEL curriculum only to those teachers whose students demonstrate a propensity towards

academic success or whose students were already reading at a higher level.

The use of archival data prior to the COVID-19 Pandemic was to allow the researcher to gather and evaluate results from four consecutive years (2015-2016 through 2018-2019) of implementation. An additional fifth year of data (2014-2015) was collected for establishing baseline equivalence. Additionally, after the pandemic had subsided and schools returned to in-person classes, grant funding was discontinued, and some schools were not able to afford the continuation of the initiative due to associated costs. Hence, Year One data (2014-2015) served as the pretest component of the research project, while Year Five data (2018-2019) served as the posttest.

This study proposed to compare two approaches for addressing academic achievement in ELA of third through fifth-grade students attending elementary schools in an urban setting. The first approach, assigned to the treatment group, used the literacy-based curriculum developed by *Cloud9World Corp.* This curriculum specifically focuses on assisting students with academic growth in literacy while instilling in them behaviors associated with positive social-emotional growth.

For the control group, no specified treatment was applied. To that effect, the strategy was consistent with traditional literacy instructional techniques used in schools for addressing academic growth in literacy. As no specific curriculum was assigned to the control group, individual schools chose to use materials other than those of the treatment schools.

Subjects

The subjects for the study consisted of students attending 10 elementary schools in the Miami Dade Public School System. As stated previously, these schools had all been designated as "persistently lowest

achieving" by the ETO. During the first school year of implementation of the treatment (2015-2016), 2,073 students were enrolled in grades K-5 in the treatment schools, while 1,989 were enrolled in K-5 in the control schools. The breakdown, per group, of the demographics by race is as follows: Treatment schools (n = 2,073) – White (0.4%), Black (92.6%), Hispanic (6%) and other (1.2%); Control schools (n = 1,989) – White (1.4%), Black (68.3%), Hispanic (26%) and other (4.2%). Additionally, 91.4% of the students in the treatment schools qualified for free or reduced lunch, while 97.1% of the control school students did.

During the fourth school year of the study (2018-2019), 1,902 students were enrolled in grades K-5 in the treatment schools, while 1,783 were enrolled in K-5 in the control schools. The breakdown, per group, of the demographics by race during the fourth year is as follows: Treatment schools (n = 1,902) – White (1.0%), Black (87.8%), Hispanic (10.3%) and other (0.8%); Control schools (n = 1,783) – White (1.1%), Black (71.9%), Hispanic (28.7%) and other (0.7%). Additionally, 86.8% of the students in the treatment schools qualified for free or reduced lunch, while 97.8% of the control schools.

Variables and Treatments

The independent variable in this study is the curriculum applied in each school. The use of the literacy-based curriculum developed by *Cloud9World Corp* was assigned to the treatment group. To reiterate, this curriculum was specifically designed to assist student growth in literacy while addressing behaviors associated with positive social-emotional growth. No specified treatment was applied to the control group. Individual schools assigned to the control group utilized materials not associated with the SEL-specific curriculum.

The treatment curriculum was first introduced to the treatment schools during full-school faculty and staff presentations at each school during required meetings. The dates and times of these meetings varied between August and September as each school elected to start with its first set of character strengths. Prior to the implementation of the intervention, schools were tasked with selecting eight character strengths from a list of 30 provided by *Cloud9World* (see Appendix) that as a school, they wanted to focus on. As such, it is possible not all schools focused on the same set of character strengths. Additionally, schools were permitted to change character strengths annually to account for students who were promoted to the next grade level.

Representatives of *Cloud9World* conducted school faculty training sessions to introduce each school to the curriculum materials. During these sessions, faculty and staff members were given opportunities to review each character strength being introduced in the coming year (one strength per month) and the books associated with the curriculum. After the initial review, best practices of the immersion rollout process were discussed. These face-to-face introduction sessions took place at the start of every school year during the study to ensure that newly hired teachers had a working knowledge and understanding of the program, and that every staff member was familiar with the character strengths they would be incorporating as part of instruction throughout the year.

A counselor in each of the treatment schools was designated as the point person if problems arose. As part of continuous follow-up, every trimester, a *Cloud9World* representative visited each school counselor to join him or her in evaluating implementation fidelity through the process of walk-throughs, answering questions, and

introducing any new support materials. Together, the counselor and the *Cloud9World* representative examined program data each year to confirm the fidelity of the implementation of the initiative.

Although problem behaviors were tracked, the dependent variable of interest for this study was student academic achievement in literacy. As such, only the academic achievement data reported was analyzed. Data regarding academic achievement was collected using standard achievement school report forms for reporting assessment data.

Data Collection and Variables

Test data collection formally began during the first year of implementation of the curriculum during the 2015-2016 school year and was completed at the culmination of the 2018-2019 school year. As stated previously, data from the 2014-2015 school year was collected to establish baseline equivalence.

At the completion of each school year, students in grades three through five were given a state mandated standardized assessment regarding English Literacy Achievement (ELA). The corresponding ELA results of each designated school in the study was made available to the administration through the Florida Department of Education (FLDOE) School Reporting System. The data from these reports was made available for this study for each year of the study's duration.

As stated above, the dependent variable in this study is academic achievement in ELA as measured by such tests. The reports made available for this study reflected the percentage of students meeting proficiency or above in ELA on the assessment. While individual student scores were not made available, the overall outcomes of each individual school in the

study were made available. This allowed the data to be analyzed holistically.

While the use of end-of-year state standardized tests to evaluate student improvement year to year has come into question due to the difference in student populations from one to the next, this study chose to utilize them due to a focus on the longitudinal impact of the treatment curriculum. For example, the students in kindergarten during year one of the study were those in third at the conclusion, demonstrating the impact on grade level results of the program over time. Similarly, first graders were in fourth grade, and second graders were in fifth. This is important to note, as the elementary curriculum is grade level focused between lower (between grades one and three) and upper (between grades four and five) elementary.

Initial statistical analysis of the data was performed using descriptive statistics on various variables and factors associated with either student demographics or ELA outcomes. A Cohen's *d* analysis was performed to evaluate baseline equivalence during the first year of implementation. An ANCOVA test was used to adjust for covariates that may impact any post-intervention differences between groups in outcomes.

Results

To answer the research question proposed in this study, a number of statistical tests were utilized. The data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were first generated. The descriptive statistics assisted in describing and summarizing the data to provide a better understanding of the distribution of the variables. The descriptive statistics run on the Free and Reduced Lunch Count for the control schools ($M =$

386.3, $SD = 124.6$) and the treatment schools ($M = 379.0$, $SD = 50.9$) revealed the means of the two groups to be similar but the standard deviation to be quite greater for the control group. Similarly, the descriptive statistics run on the Minority Count for the control schools ($M = 391.0$, $SD = 136.0$) and the treatment schools ($M = 413.0$, $SD = 70.5$) revealed the means of the two groups to be not very far apart but the standard deviation to be quite greater for the control group.

This data was used for the purpose of evaluating baseline equivalence via a Cohen's d test. Specifically, a Cohen's d test was run on these two separate variables, Free and Reduced Lunch Count and Minority Count, as these characteristics may have an impact on outcomes associated with the treatment. As stated previously, the purpose of these tests was to help determine effect-size during the first year of implementation.

The results of these tests indicate a moderate effect when evaluating Free and Reduced Lunch Count numbers (Cohen's $d = 0.08$) when compared with Cohen's guidelines (moderate effect, $0.05 \leq d \leq 0.25$)

and Minority Count numbers, as defined by the United States Census Bureau (Cohen's $d = 0.20$). These findings reveal that a statistical adjustment is required to satisfy baseline equivalence. According to the What Works Clearinghouse Group (n.d.), utilizing an ANCOVA analysis to evaluate the data in such cases is recommended.

To evaluate the ELA achievement data, both descriptive statistics and t-tests were run. Descriptive data were used as an initial analysis tool to evaluate frequencies and mean differences between the control group and treatment group during the four-year period. Table 1 shows the mean results from the descriptive statistics run on ELA proficiency data for the 2014-2015 school year. Table 2 reflects the same for the 2018-2019 school year for the same ten schools. Students are given a level rating based upon the results of their exams. Levels range from 1 (Poor) to 5 (Exemplary), While the hope is for students to score at a Level 5 rating, Level 3 (Progressing) and Level 4 (Proficient) are considered acceptable. Hence, student results were divided by those scoring in Level 1 or 2 and those scoring Level 3 or above.

Table 1*ELA 2014-2015 Mean Proficiency Results*

	Control Schools			Treatment Schools		
	# of Students	% of Students (Level 3 and Above)	# of Students	# of Students (Level 3 and Above)	% of Students (Level 3 and Above)	
Third Grade						
	50	9	18.0%	72	27	37.5%
	113	41	36.3%	89	29	32.6%
	50	14	28.0%	57	25	43.9%
	54	13	24.1%	55	19	34.5%
	54	12	22.2%	86	32	37.2%
Total	271	89	25.7%	359	132	37.1%
Fourth Grade						
	34	11	32.4%	70	30	42.9%
	97	35	36.1%	91	43	47.3%
	43	22	51.2%	52	21	40.4%
	53	15	28.3%	41	13	31.7%
	40	6	15.0%	60	30	50.0%
Total	267	89	32.6%	314	137	42.5%
Fifth Grade						
	29	7	24.1%	63	35	55.6%
	76	21	27.6%	63	36	57.1%
	45	11	24.4%	46	12	26.1%
	66	26	39.4%	56	22	39.3%
	43	15	34.9%	78	35	44.9%
Total	259	80	30.1%	306	140	44.6%

Table 2*ELA 2018-2019 Mean Proficiency Results*

	Control Schools			Treatment Schools		
	# of Students	% of Students (Level 3 and Above)	# of Students	# of Students	% of Students (Level 3 and Above)	# of Students
Third Grade						
	47	15	31.9%	94	37	39.4%
	49	15	30.6%	63	31	49.2%
	60	19	31.7%	46	28	60.9%
	69	24	34.8%	40	18	45.0%
	40	7	17.5%	74	47	63.5%
Total	265	80	29.3%	317	161	51.6%
Fourth Grade						
	38	17	44.7%	78	47	60.3%
	55	19	34.5%	49	32	65.3%
	52	22	42.3%	40	21	52.5%
	63	15	23.8%	47	24	51.1%
	31	10	32.3%	56	40	71.4%
Total	239	83	35.5%	270	164	60.1%
Fifth Grade						
	33	10	30.3%	79	43	54.4%
	60	26	43.3%	74	31	41.9%
	46	13	28.3%	45	23	51.1%
	50	20	40.0%	30	15	50.0%
	44	20	45.5%	78	45	57.7%
Total	233	89	37.5%	306	157	51.0%

Tests for Normality

One of the more common errors in statistical analysis is the assumption that the data follows a normal distribution; in other words, the researcher assumes that the populations from which the samples come are normally distributed. To avoid this error, using SPSS, a Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted on pretest and posttest data to check for normality on the total student populations of the control and treatment

schools. The results of the test indicate that both sets of data follow a normal distribution $W(6) = .898$, $p = .364$ for the pretest groupings and $W(6) = .918$, $p = .494$ for the posttest groupings.

ELA Achievement Data

To evaluate the ELA achievement data, both descriptive statistics and ANCOVA tests were conducted. The descriptive data from these reports were first evaluated to see if there were any noticeable differences in the

means between the two groups. A review of the pretest results did reflect a noticeable difference between the Control Group and the Treatment Group. Still, a review of the posttest data appeared to reveal a much larger increase in the Treatment Group numbers than the Control Group as a whole and on two grade levels, third and fourth.

Subsequently, an ANCOVA was run, accounting for any interaction effects of the two categorical variables: Free and Reduced Lunch (FRL) Count and Minority Count. First, to control for any impact socioeconomic status may have, the FRL Count data was set as the covariate, with treatment set as the fixed factor and posttest results as the dependent variable. The results of this analysis revealed a statistically significant difference [$F(1,28) = 15.8, p < .001$] between the treatment and control group outcomes while adjusting for socioeconomic status as measured by Free and Reduced Lunch Count numbers.

Similarly, an ANCOVA test was run to control for any impact of Minority Count, which was set as the covariate, with treatment set as the fixed factor and posttest results as the dependent variable again. The results of this analysis reveal a statistically significant difference [$F(1,28) = 41.60, p < .011$] between the treatment and control group outcomes while adjusting for minority status as measured by Minority Count numbers.

These tests were followed by a series of t-tests to determine where key differences may have occurred. The first was an independent samples t-test between the control and treatment groups to determine if there were any statistically significant differences in the first-year results. The results of this analysis revealed that there was a significant difference between the two groups at baseline, $t(28) = -3.6, p = .001$. Second and third paired samples t-tests were performed, analyzing the change in results

between the pretest and posttest for the Control Group and Treatment Group, respectively. The outcome of the t-test on the Control Group pre and posttest data revealed that there was no statistically significant difference between the two tests, $t(28) = -1.47, p = .151$. By contrast, the results of the t-test on the Treatment Group pre and posttest data revealed that there was a statistically significant difference between the two tests, $t(28) = -3.97, p = .001$. One final independent samples t-test was conducted between the posttest results of the two groups. The results of that test revealed once again a statistically significant difference between the two groups' outcomes, $t(28) = -6.52, p = <.001$.

To expand on these findings and based upon a review of the descriptive statistics, a second series of t-tests were conducted to evaluate the data by grade level. The findings of the initial six t-tests were interesting (see Figure 1). In this series, the pretest and posttest results of each grade level within each group were evaluated. The results revealed no statistically significant differences in pretest and posttest percentages for the following groups: 3rd-grade control group ($t(4) = -0.906, p = .208$); 4th-grade control group ($t(4) = -0.585, p = .294$); and 5th-grade treatment group ($t(4) = -0.941, p = .199$).

By contrast, the results revealed statistically significant differences in pretest and posttest percentages for the other three groups: 3rd-grade treatment group ($t(4) = -3.589, p = .011$); 4th-grade treatment group ($t(4) = -11.386, p = .0001$); and 5th-grade control group ($t(4) = -2.791, p = .024$). Accordingly, one final t-test was conducted. The pretest data of the 5th-grade control and treatment groups was analyzed. The results of this test demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the two 5th-grade groups' outcomes, $t(4) = -2.90, p = .0022$, with the treatment group having

significantly higher percentages. This suggests that the high pretest percentages of

the 5th-grade treatment group had an impact on improvement numbers.

Figure 1

Data by Grade Level

Alternate Text: Statistically significant increases were found between pretest treatment and posttest treatment in grades three and four and between pretest control and posttest control in grade five. No statistically significant increases were found between pretest control and posttest control in grades three and four and between pretest treatment and posttest treatment in grade five.

Discussion

Findings

This study identified the impact of a literacy-based social-emotional learning curriculum initiative on ELA academic achievement over a four-year period. Statistically significant effects were observed, which suggest that providing students attending an urban elementary school program with a high minority and free and reduced lunch population with literacy-based character development learning opportunities can be an effective tool for raising student academic achievement.

Limitations and Future Directions

A couple of limitations to this study should be addressed. First, the process by which the participating schools were selected did not allow for randomization of subjects. By the nature of the program, all students attending a participant school were considered part of the study. An ill effect of this action was that the two grouping student population sizes were slightly imbalanced prior to the implementation of the study. Second, new hires annually may have made the implementation of the literacy curriculum less fluid. Due to the nature of teacher turnover and the impact on classroom climate, the consistent

implementation of the treatment curriculum may have been somewhat difficult.

Also, the use of end of year standardized test data is a limitation as the year-to-year grade level populations change significantly. Additionally, this study was limited to numbers and percentages of students achieving proficiency or not on such tests on a macro level. Individual treatment and control group schools were not evaluated independently, only collectively. It may potentially benefit future studies to narrow down the sample groups to one grade level and track their achievement rates over time.

Conclusions

This study sought to answer a question about the impact of a literacy-based, social emotional learning curriculum on ELA academic achievement in urban elementary schools classified as "persistently lowest-achieving" schools. Specifically, the study evaluated the use of the *Cloud9World* literacy curriculum program on improving student achievement on the end-of-year grade-level assessment

required by the state. An analysis of the data demonstrated that the impact of the program on student achievement in ELA on these assessments was statistically significant.

In interacting with staff and students, overall satisfaction with the use of the program was discovered in the treatment schools. Additionally, though not part of the study specifically, administrators and teachers found the program to be beneficial in opening doors for dialogue leading to a better understanding of positive social skills. Subsequently, these dialogues lead to expanded opportunities for redirecting student problem behavior.

The findings of the data and conversations support research literature on the benefits of inclusion of instruction aimed at the growth of students in social-emotional learning (e.g., CASEL, 2024; Wilkins et al., 2023; Weissberg & Cascarion, 2013; Jones & Bouffard, 2012). Additionally, the results of this study indicate that the implementation of a literacy-based curriculum may be associated with improved academic achievement.

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Appendix

List of Character Strengths Curriculum Provided by Cloud9World

- Gentleness
- Commitment
- Creativity
- Patience
- Citizenship
- Tolerance
- Courage
- Gratitude
- Responsibility
- Individuality
- Confidence
- Kindness
- Integrity
- Generosity
- Cooperation
- Love
- Humbleness
- Honesty
- Respect
- Compassion
- Acceptance
- Perseverance
- Loyalty
- Self-control
- Joyfulness
- Forgiveness
- Determination
- Unity
- Wisdom
- Humor